

Advanced Biomass Catalytic Conversion to Middle Distillates in Molten Salts

ABC-Salt is a four-year platform funded by Horizon 2020 that will validate at laboratory scale a novel route to produce sustainable liquid biofuels (middle distillates) from various lignocellulosic waste streams for the transport industry.

- Validating a novel way to produce sustainable liquid biofuels at laboratory scale
- Nine European partners collaborating until 2022
- Open access summer schools and workshops available

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 Birmingham

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 German Aerospace Center

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Norwegian University
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www.abc-salt.eu

www.linkedin.com/company/abc-salt/

[@H2020_ABC_SALT](https://twitter.com/H2020_ABC_SALT)

abc-salt@aston.ac.uk

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ABC-Salt – Advanced Biomass Catalytic Conversion to Middle Distillates in Molten Salts